

Kinetics and Mechanism of Complex Formation by Molybdenum(VI) and Vanadium(V) with Benzo-, *o*-Methylbenzo- and *o*-Hydroxybenzohydroxamic Acids in Aqueous Solution

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Kinetics of formation of complexes in the reaction of Mo^{VI} at pH 7.5–8.5 and of V^v at pH 2.5–3.5 with benzo-, *o*-methylbenzo- and *o*-hydroxybenzohydroxamic acids in aqueous solution have been studied by stopped-flow spectrophotometry. Data have been analysed for evaluation of rate constants and the corresponding activation parameters and plausible reaction mechanisms assigned. The reactions appear to involve associative, *I_a*, processes with significant dependence on the nature of the entering ligand.

Interest in the coordination chemistry of vanadium and molybdenum has increased considerably due to recognition of the important role of these two metals in biological systems¹. In acidic or weakly alkaline media molybdenum(VI) in the form of MoO₂²⁺ forms octahedral complexes of the type MoO₂L₄ having the two oxo groups in *cis*-positions with various ligands. Kinetic studies on the formation and dissociation of many such complexes have been reported²; these include the ligands

hydroxamic acids with molybdenum(VI) and vanadium(V) appeared worthy of investigation and results of some such studies are reported in this communication.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF FIRST ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF THE HYDROXAMIC ACIDS (LH₂) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

LH ₂	p <i>K_a</i>		
	35°	40°	45°
C ₆ H ₅ CO(NHOH) (BHA)	8.54 ± 0.01	8.52 ± 0.01	8.50 ± 0.01
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (CH ₃)CO- (NHOH) (MHA)	8.50 ± 0.01	8.47 ± 0.01	8.44 ± 0.01
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ (OH)CO- (NHOH) (SHA)	7.90 ± 0.01	7.85 ± 0.01	7.80 ± 0.01

8-hydroxyquinoline and derivatives, di- and trihydroxybenzene, alizarine sulphonate, nitrilotriacetate, ethylenediaminetetraacetate, etc. For vanadium(V) similar investigations have been reported on complex formation by VO₂⁺ in acidic media with ligands like ethylenediaminetetraacetate, ethylenediaminediacetate, nitrilotriacetate, etc.³, and also with mandelic and thiolactic acids⁴. In view of the known⁵ role of the hydroxamate group in biologically significant ligands, kinetics of complex formation by

TABLE 2—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANT (*K_H*) for MoO₄²⁻ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. (°C)	35°	40°	45°
log <i>K_H</i>	4.25 ± 0.01	4.41 ± 0.01	4.56 ± 0.02

Results and Discussion

For molybdenum(VI)-hydroxamic acid (LH₂) reactions, since complex formation even in presence of excess LH₂ decreases with increase in pH, it follows that this represents a truly reversible system where the reverse reaction cannot be ignored and hence the observed rate constant, *k_{obs}*, corresponds to that for approach to the equilibrium state. The p*K_a* values corresponding to the first acid dissociation of all the hydroxamic acids (LH₂) at the experimental temperatures (35°, 40°, 45°) were evaluated from the corresponding Δ*H* and Δ*S* values reported earlier⁶. However, these strictly correspond to an ionic strength of 1 mol dm⁻³. From literature data on glycine, acetic acid and salicylic acid⁷, it is known that effect of ionic strength (*I*) on p*K_a* is not significant and this is therefore likely to hold good for the hydroxamic acids also. Therefore, as a reasonable approximation the p*K_a* values at *I* = 1 mol dm⁻³ could be used for

$I = 3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and these pK_a values are given in Table 1. Since all these pK_a values are in the range 7.8–8.55, in the range of experimental pH the solutions were self-buffered. It is known⁸ that even at a concentration of $\sim 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ only mono-nuclear species of Mo^{VI} are present in solution at $\text{pH} \geq 4.8$. Literature data⁹ on the equilibrium,

and ΔH and ΔS values corresponding to K_H at $I = 3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4) enabled evaluation of K_H values at the experimental temperatures and these are given in Table 2. There is evidence¹⁰ that the protonated species $\text{MoO}_3(\text{OH})^-$ is possibly $\text{MoO}_2(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$. The observed variation of k_{obs} with $[\text{H}^+]$ and total $[\text{LH}_2]$ is in conformity with the following reaction scheme :

Step (3), however, is most likely to be a two-step process as follows :

From this it follows that

$$k_1 = (k'_1 k'_2) / (k'_{-1} + k'_2) \text{ and}$$

$$k_2 = (k'_{-1} k'_{-2}) / (k'_{-1} + k'_2)$$

Based on the overall process (eqn. 3) the rate for approach to the equilibrium, V_{eq} is given by

$$V_{\text{eq}} = \{k_1[\text{LH}^-] + k_2\} [\text{MoO}_2(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-] \quad (5)$$

Any possible reaction involving MoO_4^{2-} may be virtually non-contributing since with any ligand $\text{MoO}_2(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ is known to react faster than MoO_4^{2-} by a factor of 10^4 (as with 8-hydroxyquinoline)¹¹ to 10^6 (as with catechol)¹². From eqns. (1) and (2) it follows (T_L and T_{Mo} are the total concentrations of LH_2 and Mo^{VI} in the solution),

$$[\text{LH}^-] = K_a T_L / \{K_a + [\text{H}^+]\} \quad (6)$$

and $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{OH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-] = \frac{K_H [\text{H}^+] T_{\text{Mo}}}{\{1 + K_H [\text{H}^+]\}} \quad (7)$

Substituting these values in eqn. (5) we get,

$$V_{\text{eq}} = \left\{ \frac{k_1 K_a T_L}{K_a + [\text{H}^+]} + k_2 \right\} \frac{K_H T_{\text{Mo}} [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_H [\text{H}^+]} \quad (8)$$

Since K_H is of the order of 10^4 and $[\text{H}^+]$ is of the order of 10^{-8} in the experimental solutions ($\text{pH} 7.5\text{--}8.5$), $K_H [\text{H}^+] \ll 1$ and eqn. (8) therefore transforms into

$$V_{\text{eq}} \approx \frac{k_1 K_H K_a T_L T_{\text{Mo}} [\text{H}^+]}{K_a + [\text{H}^+]} + k_2 K_H T_{\text{Mo}} [\text{H}^+] \quad (9)$$

Since in the experimental solutions $T_L \gg T_{\text{Mo}}$, the experimentally observed pseudo-first order rate constant is

$$k_{\text{obs}} \approx \frac{k_1 K_H K_a T_L [\text{H}^+]}{K_a + [\text{H}^+]} + k_2 K_H [\text{H}^+] \quad (10)$$

Hence,

$$\frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{K_H [\text{H}^+]} \approx \frac{k_1 K_a T_L}{K_a + [\text{H}^+]} + k_2 \quad (11)$$

Values of k_1 and k_2 were obtained graphically (also checked by least-square procedure) using eqn. (11) with known values of K_a and K_H (see Tables 1 and 2). These are given in Table 3 with the corresponding values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger evaluated from k_1 and k_2 values at three different temperatures using Eyring equation as usual.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANTS AND CORRESPONDING ACTIVATION PARAMETERS* FOR THE Mo^{IV}-HYDROXAMIC ACID (LH₂) SYSTEMS

$I = 3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} (\text{NaClO}_4), \text{pH} = 7.5-8.5$

LH ₂	$10^{-4} k_1 (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$			$10^{-2} k_2 (\text{s}^{-1})$		
	35°	40°	45°	35°	40°	45°
BHA	7.20 ± 0.04	7.97 ± 0.05	8.69 ± 0.03	1.04 ± 0.02	1.10 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.02
	$\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 12.7 \pm 0.5; \Delta S_1^\ddagger = -111.5 \pm 1.3$			$\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 7.7 \pm 0.3; \Delta S_2^\ddagger = -182.5 \pm 2.2$		
MHA	5.60 ± 0.04	6.40 ± 0.05	6.95 ± 0.03	0.58 ± 0.02	0.64 ± 0.01	0.68 ± 0.02
	$\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 18.6 \pm 0.7; \Delta S_1^\ddagger = -94.7 \pm 1.1$			$\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 13.2 \pm 0.4; \Delta S_2^\ddagger = -169.3 \pm 1.9$		
SHA	12.17 ± 0.02	13.63 ± 0.03	15.62 ± 0.02	1.90 ± 0.01	2.10 ± 0.01	2.40 ± 0.01
	$\Delta H_1^\ddagger = 17.5 \pm 0.7; \Delta S_1^\ddagger = -91.5 \pm 1.0$			$\Delta H_2^\ddagger = 18.0 \pm 0.7; \Delta S_2^\ddagger = -143.7 \pm 1.7$		

* ΔH^\ddagger values in kJ mol^{-1} , ΔS^\ddagger values in $\text{JK}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}$.

 TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANTS FOR 1 : 1 COMPLEX FORMATION IN Mo^{VI}-LIGAND SYSTEMS

Temp. = 25°

Reacting ligand	$k_f (\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1})$	Ref.
8-Hydroxyquinoline	4.5×10^6	11
8-Hydroxyquinolinate (1-)	1.5×10^8	11
8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonate (1-)	3.9×10^6	13
8-Hydroxyquinoline-5-sulphonate (2-)	4.0×10^7	13
Catechol	1.9×10^8	12
1,2,4-Trihydroxybenzene	6.6×10^7	14
H ₂ edta (2-)	2.3×10^5	15
BHA (1-)	6.1×10^4 ^a	Present work
MHA (1-)	4.2×10^4 ^a	Present work
SHA (1-)	9.6×10^4 ^a	Present work

^a Estimated from the ΔH_1^\ddagger and ΔS_1^\ddagger values (see Table 3).

A comparison of the rate constants for formation of Mo^{VI} complexes with different ligands as given in Table 4 is interesting. It follows that rate of complex formation is significantly dependent on the nature of the entering ligand. Thus, 8-hydroxyquinolinate reacts faster than benzohydroxamate by a factor of 10^4 and at 25° the k_1 values for reactions of BHA, MHA and SHA are in the ratio of 1 : 0.69 : 1.57. This significant dependence of the rate on the nature of the ligand suggests some sort of associative mechanism in keeping with the first step in eqn. (4) as the rate-determining step where the unidentate binding of LH⁻ through replacement of an aqua ligand bound to the Mo^{VI} presumably occurs by an associative pathway, more likely an I_a process

where Mo-L bond formation and Mo-OH₂ bond dissociation are synchronous. In view of this the first bond formation is rate-determining and in eqn. (4) $k_2' \gg k_{-1}'$ and therefore, $k_1 \approx k_1'$ and $k_2 \approx k_{-1}'k_{-2}'/k_2'$.

Analysis of the data for the V^V-hydroxamic acid systems indicates, as for Mo^{VI} reactions, a one-step kinetic process with rate showing dependence on $[\text{H}^+]$ and total $[\text{LH}_2]$ which are in conformity with the following reaction scheme for formation of the 1 : 2 complex (*loc cit.*):

(13)

All the V^V species are shown having coordination number 5 or 6, which is in conformity with the

well-known¹⁶ tendency of V^v to expand its coordination number from 4 to 5 or even 6, and that in alkaline media the vanadate species¹⁶ is likely to be VO₂(OH)₃²⁻ and hence the monoprotonated species is likely to be VO(OH)₄⁻ (see eqn. 12).

Under the condition $T_L \gg T_V$, this leads to

$$k'_{obs} = k K'_H T_L [H^+] / \{1 + K'_H [H^+]\} \quad (14)$$

Hence,

$$T_L / k'_{obs} = 1/k + 1/k K'_H [H^+] \quad (15)$$

where, $k = k'_1 k'_2 / (k'_-1 + k'_2)$. Making use of eqn. (15), values of k and K'_H were evaluated graphically (also checked by least-square procedure) from k'_{obs} values obtained at different pH and T_L . The K'_H and k values with ΔH and ΔS values corresponding to K'_H and ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values corresponding to k are given in Tables 5 and 6 respectively. Results indicate that complexation of V^v proceeds faster by a factor of ca. 10 compared to that of Mo^{VI}.

TABLE 5—VALUES OF PROTONATION CONSTANT (K'_H) FOR VO(OH)₄⁻ AS OBTAINED FROM ANALYSIS OF KINETIC DATA

$I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄)

System	$10^{-4} K'_H \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$			
	20°	25°	30°	35°
V ^v -BHA	1.89 ± 0.08	1.27 ± 0.06	0.79 ± 0.08	0.60 ± 0.05
V ^v -MHA	1.95 ± 0.10	1.17 ± 0.08	0.79 ± 0.07	0.53 ± 0.06
V ^v -SHA	1.96 ± 0.06	1.23 ± 0.08	0.74 ± 0.10	0.55 ± 0.05
Average				
(K'_H) values	1.93 ± 0.08	1.22 ± 0.07	0.77 ± 0.08	0.56 ± 0.05

At 25° ($I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) the (K'_H) value quoted in literature¹⁷ from equilibrium studies is $0.61 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Experimental

Aqueous solutions of molybdenum(vi) and vanadium(v) were prepared from ammonium molybdate and ammonium vanadate (G.R., E. Merck) which were standardised gravimetrically as usual¹⁸, molybdenum as oxinate, MoO₂(C₉H₆ON)₂, and vanadium as silver vanadate, Ag₃VO₄.

Benzohydroxamic acid (BHA) and its *ortho*-methyl (MHA) and *ortho*-hydroxy (SHA) derivatives were prepared in pure form as reported earlier⁶. Sodium perchlorate was purified by recrystallisation twice from aqueous solution

followed by drying at 120°. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Distilled water redistilled using an all-glass still after addition of some amount of KOH and KMnO₄ was used in preparing all solutions.

TABLE 6—VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT (k) AND THE CORRESPONDING ACTIVATION PARAMETERS* FOR 1 : 2 COMPLEX FORMATION IN V^v-HYDROXAMIC ACID (LH₂) SYSTEMS

$I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄), pH = 2.5–3.5

LH ₂	$10^{-3} k'_H \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
	20°	25°	30°	35°
BHA	3.41 ± 0.03	5.68 ± 0.03	7.69 ± 0.05	11.62 ± 0.06
	$\Delta H^\ddagger = 60.1 \pm 0.2; \Delta S^\ddagger = 27.3 \pm 1.2$			
MHA	2.77 ± 0.03	4.54 ± 0.03	7.14 ± 0.04	10.41 ± 0.05
	$\Delta H^\ddagger = 64.1 \pm 0.3; \Delta S^\ddagger = 39.1 \pm 1.9$			
SHA	1.75 ± 0.02	2.50 ± 0.02	3.50 ± 0.03	5.10 ± 0.05
	$\Delta H^\ddagger = 52.4 \pm 0.2; \Delta S^\ddagger = -4.8 \pm 0.5$			

* ΔH^\ddagger values in kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS^\ddagger values in JK⁻¹mol⁻¹.

Absorbance spectra were recorded using a Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer (Jena, Germany). pH measurements were made with a precision PHM-26 pH-meter (Radiometer, Copenhagen) with glass-calomel electrode system, and all kinetic studies were made using a SF-3A stopped-flow spectrophotometer (Hi-Tech, England) coupled with a microprocessor unit. The flow module of the SF-3A had thermostatic arrangement for maintaining the reacting solutions and the observation cell at a desired temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$).

The pH meter with its electrode system was calibrated with standard solutions of known [H⁺] so that from a pH vs $-\log [H^+]$ calibration curve the exact [H⁺] corresponding to a measured pH could be evaluated for each of the experimental temperatures. Spectral observations indicated that in presence of excess of the hydroxamic acids, LH₂ (Mo^{VI}, 0.0005 mol dm⁻³; LH₂, 0.005 mol dm⁻³) appreciable complex (yellow colour) formation occurs in the pH range 7.5–8.5, complex formation decreasing with increase in pH, and the rate of formation of the complex could be followed conveniently at 400 nm. By spectrophotometric mole ratio method the composition of the complex was shown to be 1 : 1 between Mo^{VI} and the hydroxamate ligand. For rate measurements pseudo-first order conditions were maintained in the experimental

solution (Mo^{VI} , $0.0005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; LH_2 , $0.005\text{--}0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and ionic strength was adjusted to 3 mol dm^{-3} by adding requisite amount of NaClO_4 . pH values of the solutions were adjusted with NaOH or HClO_4 as needed. The microprocessor recorded the absorbance vs time for the reaction and from this the observed value of the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was also evaluated by the microprocessor. Average values from at least three independent runs were accepted.

Vanadium(v) formed a violet coloured complex with excess of benzohydroxamic acid at pH 2.5–3.5 having an absorbance maximum at 460 nm; the complex formation was virtually complete in this pH range ascertained spectrophotometrically. The other two hydroxamic acids behaved similarly. By spectrophotometric mole method the composition of the complex was found to be 1 : 2 between V^{V} and the hydroxamate ligand. The rate of complex formation was followed under pseudo-first order conditions (V^{V} , $0.0005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; LH_2 , $0.005\text{--}0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) at different pH (2.5–3.5) and an ionic strength of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} (adjusted with NaClO_4) by stopped-flow spectrophotometry at 460 nm, and the data were analysed for evaluation of the pseudo-first order rate constants as for the Mo^{VI} reactions mentioned above.

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